

Public Health Nursing In The Digital Health Era: Applications, Effectiveness, And Current Evidence Of Mobile Health Applications

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ABSTRACT

Mobile health applications are gaining increasing importance as a key component of digital transformation in healthcare. Particularly in the field of public health nursing, these technologies are enhancing the accessibility of healthcare services, supporting continuity of care, and improving health outcomes. This review examines the applications, contributions, and impacts of mobile health applications on health outcomes in public health nursing, based on the current literature. The findings indicate that mobile health applications are effective across a wide range of areas, including chronic disease management, maternal and child health, immunization services, infectious disease management, and health behavior change. These applications enhance treatment adherence by strengthening individuals' self-management skills, improve clinical outcomes, and facilitate access to healthcare services. Additionally, they contribute to improving the quality of care by supporting healthcare professionals' clinical decision-making processes. Evidence shows that mobile health interventions strengthen early diagnosis, monitoring, and intervention processes, particularly in preventive health services such as cancer screenings and vaccination programs. All these findings demonstrate that mobile health applications contribute to reducing health inequities and improving the quality of care. However, the effective use of these technologies depends on the active participation of healthcare professionals, digital health literacy, data security, and adherence to ethical standards. Consequently, mobile health applications are regarded as innovative tools that contribute to improving public health in community nursing. However, to ensure sustainable and effective use, it is necessary to enhance the digital

competencies of healthcare professionals and develop appropriate health policies.

Keywords: Mobile Health, Public Health Nursing, Digital Health.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid advancements in digital health technologies are fundamentally transforming the way healthcare services are delivered. Today, various digital technologies are used to facilitate the delivery of healthcare services. One such technology is mobile health applications. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines mobile health as the use of mobile wireless technologies for public health (1). Mobile health interventions are designed to improve healthcare delivery processes, enabling the provision of healthcare services via mobile devices and facilitating individuals' active participation in their own health management (2). These interventions are used both to increase demand for health services and expand access to health information through targeted communication with individuals, and to provide support to health professionals in education, diagnosis, and patient management processes (1,2).

Mobile health applications facilitate access to specialized healthcare services by eliminating geographical barriers, particularly for individuals living in rural and hard-to-reach areas, thereby making a significant contribution to reducing health inequalities (3).

Nurses are healthcare professionals who take direct responsibility for the protection and promotion of individuals' health and are in the closest contact with patients. By assuming multifaceted roles such as providing clinical care, monitoring treatment processes, delivering health education, and preventing diseases, they occupy a critical position in ensuring the continuity and quality of healthcare services (4). Increasing scientific knowledge and evolving patient needs require nurses to integrate their knowledge and skills into clinical decision-making processes to play a more effective role. In this context, mobile health applications have emerged as important digital tools that support nurses' professional practices and enhance the quality of care (5). The literature indicates that nurses use mobile health applications to enhance their professional knowledge and skills, support evidence-based

decision-making processes, improve patient care, contribute to the diagnostic process, facilitate patient and data management, and promote health. In diagnostic and clinical evaluation processes, these applications offer significant contributions in terms of supporting early diagnosis, guiding clinical decision-making processes, presenting solution options for potential health issues, and providing rapid access to up-to-date clinical information. In terms of health promotion, they enable the monitoring of individuals' health behaviors such as physical activity, nutrition, and sleep thereby strengthening preventive and supportive care practices, particularly in primary care settings (5). These applications demonstrate that mobile health apps align directly with preventive, promotive, and monitoring-focused services provided at both the individual and community levels within the scope of public health nursing; they also highlight that these apps serve as a vital digital tool for strengthening core public health nursing functions such as monitoring at-risk groups, early intervention, health education, and supporting behavior change.

For this reason, this review was conducted to present the applications of mobile health applications in public health nursing, their contributions, and their impact on health outcomes, based on the current literature.

Mobile Health Applications in the Management of Chronic Diseases

Mobile health applications are frequently used in the management of chronic diseases, particularly because they help individuals develop self-management skills, improve treatment adherence, and enhance clinical outcomes (6,7). For example, a study on a text message-based diabetes self-management support program concluded that SMS-based interventions are effective in improving blood sugar control (HbA1c), foot care behaviors, and perceptions of disease identity among diabetes patients (8). An experimental study conducted with a mobile health application among patients with hypertension revealed that the mobile health application not only created a significant difference in blood pressure control but also improved the patient's health and disease management through disease knowledge, lifestyle behaviors, healthy nutrition, and physical exercise (9). Similarly, studies have

shown that mobile health applications are effective in managing chronic conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, asthma, COPD, epilepsy, and severe mental illnesses (10-15).

Increasing the use of effective mobile health applications in the management of chronic diseases which account for a significant portion of the global disease burden offers important benefits. These benefits include reducing the care burden on healthcare providers and families, enabling individuals to live as independently as possible, fostering more active participation in treatment processes, and strengthening patient-centered care (6-7). In addition, there are benefits such as reducing unnecessary hospitalizations and emergency department visits and thereby lowering healthcare costs as individuals take greater control over their conditions (16). However, the effectiveness of mobile health applications depends not only on the availability of technology but also on active guidance and support from healthcare professionals. A study published by Muralidharan and colleagues (2017) found that, in addition to mobile health technology, the support of healthcare professionals yields additional positive outcomes for patients, and emphasized that mobile health interventions must be reinforced by the active participation of healthcare professionals (17).

Mobile Health Applications in Maternal and Child Health Services

One of the key areas of application for mobile health applications in public health nursing is maternal and child health services, which is a fundamental component of the field. Mobile health applications are used across a wide range of applications, including promoting healthy lifestyle behaviors during maternal and child health and prenatal care processes, improving the mother's physical and mental health (weight management, gestational diabetes, asthma control, etc.), ensuring the regular use of recommended folic acid and iron supplements during pregnancy, and increasing adherence to immunization services; and their effectiveness in these areas has been demonstrated in the literature (18-19). The integration of mobile health applications into existing maternal health services enhances women's perceptions of care quality, supports healthy behavior change, strengthens their engagement with health

services, and raises their awareness of high-risk conditions during pregnancy (20). Given the decisive impact of maternal health on a child's first five years of life (21), it can be argued that mobile health applications designed to protect and improve maternal health also have an indirect positive effect on child health. Indeed, a systematic review has shown that mobile health applications developed for pregnant women are largely feasible and well-accepted by users (18).

Mobile Health Apps in Immunization Services and the Fight Against Vaccine Hesitancy

Another important application of mobile health apps in public health nursing is in immunization services and the fight against vaccine hesitancy. Today, rising vaccine hesitancy poses a serious threat to public health. Despite the clear benefits of childhood immunization, morbidity and mortality rates from vaccine-preventable diseases continue to strain health systems, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (22). The literature has demonstrated that mobile health applications increase vaccination rates (22,23). Similarly, it has been reported that SMS reminders reduce delays in vaccination (22). The success of mobile health applications in vaccination plays a critical role in preventing infectious diseases and controlling outbreaks, which directly impact public health.

Mobile Health Applications in the Surveillance of Infectious Diseases and Outbreak Management

In developing countries, the integration of mobile health applications into infectious disease surveillance systems significantly enhances the effectiveness of public health interventions by increasing the speed, accuracy, and scope of data collection and reporting processes. While delays in traditional systems can be mitigated through mobile health applications, critical processes such as early detection, isolation, and contact tracing can also be carried out effectively at a lower cost (24). It is emphasized that public health workers must be supported by mobile technologies to effectively leverage all these advantages and increase success rates (24).

Mobile Health Apps in Health Education and Behavior Change

Furthermore, mobile health apps are used as an effective tool in health education and behavior change processes. Studies have shown that mobile health applications have positive effects on health-related behaviors and clinical outcomes in both children and adults; they represent a practical and effective intervention method that supports health behavior change (25,26). Raising awareness among individuals regarding topics such as healthy eating, physical activity, smoking cessation, and stress management can be made more systematic and continuous through mobile applications (27). These applications are actively used not only for patients but also for training healthcare providers. For example, Subramanian and colleagues (2021) used a mobile health cancer screening education app to train primary care physicians. At the end of the training, it was observed that the physicians' knowledge of common types of cancer had significantly increased, and it was demonstrated that a mobile health app is both feasible and beneficial for training physicians (28). These findings demonstrate that mobile health applications are a powerful tool in preventive healthcare and are effective in fostering healthy lifestyle behaviors, promoting behavioral change, and providing health education.

Mobile Health Applications in Community-Based Screening Programs

Another factor that influences an individual's health as much as healthy lifestyle behaviors and forms the foundation of public health is participation in community-based screening programs. Participation in screening programs ensures that existing diseases are diagnosed early and treated. These applications are effective in reducing morbidity and mortality rates associated with diseases that can be detected and treated early (29). In particular, the early detection of diseases that create a long-term care burden and increase hospital stays through cancer screenings helps reduce the economic burden on healthcare systems. A systematic literature review conducted by Salmani and colleagues (2020) in the field of mobile health found that mobile health applications have significant and positive effects on cancer screening processes and clinical health outcomes; through their multi-

component structures (information, planning, and education), they enhance patient satisfaction and quality of life; and due to their high acceptability and sustainable usage characteristics, they offer significant potential for improvement in the monitoring, management, and support of screening results (29).

In addition to all these applications, they are used in a wide variety of fields for the purpose of protecting and promoting health. They are widely used by health professionals in diverse areas such as protecting and promoting the health of older adults, home care services, mental health services, promoting school and adolescent health, and increasing health literacy.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, mobile health applications are regarded as innovative tools that enhance the quality of care in public health nursing, have the potential to reduce health inequities, and play a significant role in improving community health. These applications contribute to making health services more accessible, patient-centered, and sustainable; they also enhance the effectiveness of health systems. Mobile health applications are highly significant for promoting health and self-management of illness by offering convenience and accessibility, and this is an area that continues to evolve (6).

To ensure the widespread and effective use of mobile health applications, it is necessary to increase digital health literacy, strengthen data security and ethical standards, and develop the competencies of healthcare professionals regarding these technologies. To promote the more widespread and effective use of mobile health applications:

- Developing in-service training programs to enhance public health nurses' digital competencies regarding mobile health technologies,
- National policies and strategies should be established to integrate mobile health applications into the healthcare system,
- Digital health literacy programs should be expanded to increase access to mobile health applications for disadvantaged groups,

- Long-term, randomized controlled, and multicenter studies should be planned to evaluate the effectiveness of mobile health applications,
- It is recommended that nurses one of the professional groups best equipped to identify individuals' needs at the health promotion and prevention stages play an active role not only in the use but also in the development of mobile health applications.

DESCRIPTIONS

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